

indicated a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state and an essentially square-planar arrangement around copper(II). The trend, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ observed for the complexes, indicated that the unpaired electron is most likely in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of copper(II). This is further supported by the ratio⁶, $(g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2) \approx 4$. From the observed g values, it is evident that the metal-ligand bonds have considerable covalent character⁷. Spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{Nap}:\text{gly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ recorded in DMF showed four main peaks, evidently due to coupling of the electron with the ^{63}Cu nucleus ($I=3/2$). The peaks are broad and have the appearance of ill-resolved triplets. The breadth and triplet appearance, attributable to hyperfine splitting by nitrogen atom ($I=1$) of the ligand, provide evidence for nitrogen coordination⁸. The resolution is poor, presumably due to recording at room temperature. The \tilde{A}_{Cu} values observed (ca. 85G) for these chelates are comparable to those of the similar copper(II) complexes for which delocalisation of metal d -electron to the chelate ring has been envisaged⁹.

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Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Piperidinomethylurea

A. SABASTIYAN** and D. VENKAPPAYYA*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Tiruchirapalli-620 015

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THE present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with piperidinomethylurea, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2$ (PMU). Kinetic parameters of the non-isothermal decompositions of a selected few complexes and PMU have also been reported.

**Present address: Urumu Dhanalakshmi College, Tiruchirapalli 620 019.

Experimental

PMU¹ was prepared by reacting a 37% aqueous HCHO (20.3 g) and urea (15.0 g) mixture with piperidine (21.25 g) at $\sim 10^\circ$. The metal salt (0.02 mol) and PMU (0.02 or 0.04 mol) were dissolved separately in a suitable organic solvent (30 ml; BuOH, DMF etc.) and the two solutions were mixed and stirred at $\sim 80^\circ$ and pH ~ 7 . The resulting solid metal complex formed was washed with the hot solvent followed by ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator (Table 1). Molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectra both in solid (MgCO_3) as well as in solution (DMF) and room temperature magnetic susceptibility were measured for characterising the complexes. TG and DTA studies were carried out upto 1200° at a heating rate of 10° under static air.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF PMU COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		Metal	Anion	N
$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Green	14.10 (13.23)	15.35 (15.98)	18.55 (18.93)
$\text{NiBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Green	10.85 (11.03)	30.64 (30.01)	15.37 (15.77)
$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Green	16.75 (17.28)	- (36.50)	19.31 (20.61)
$\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Green	15.20 (14.16)	- (47.97)	9.91 (10.13)
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Brown	22.45 (21.80)	24.30 (24.33)	13.95 (14.41)
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Greenish blue	14.65 (14.17)	16.25 (15.81)	19.22 (18.73)
$\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Brown	16.25 (16.70)	41.05 (42.02)	11.36 (11.04)
$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue	12.75 (11.82)	- (23.07)	22.25 (20.84)
$\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue	10.65 (10.37)	- (32.48)	13.92 (13.71)
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Greenish blue	17.75 (18.02)	28.25 (27.23)	11.76 (11.91)

Results and Discussion

The complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with PMU are green and blue or brown respectively. They are slightly soluble in common organic solvents. The low molar conductance values ($1.9 - 3.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) indicate the non-ionic nature of the complexes except in the cases of $\text{CuX}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$) which are 1 : 2 electrolytes ($145 - 149 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in DMF and $54.5 - 58.9 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$).

In all the complexes, the carbonyl stretching vibrational mode of the free ligand observed at 1630 cm^{-1} experiences a negative shift of $30 - 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the bonding of PMU to the metal through oxygen². The peaks at $155 - 120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{O}}$ of the piperidine ring of PMU) get lowered by $80 - 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes pointing to the

coordination of the tertiary amino nitrogen² to the metal ion. Thus, in all the complexes PMU behaves as a chelating bidentate ligand. In the far-infrared region, the $\nu_{M-N} + \nu_{M-O}$ (mixed) and ν_{M-X} (X=Cl, Br) bands are observed around 300–430 and 200–300 cm^{-1} respectively. In $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the existence of bonded water has been detected based on infrared (3 570–3 510, 1 660–1 630, 850–650 cm^{-1}) and thermo-analytical data. The infrared data also reveal bidentate coordination³ of NO_3^- and ClO_4^- with Ni^{II} and SO_4^{2-} with Cu^{II} ions.

Solid state electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} -PMU complexes exhibit three bands at $\sim 10\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (\nu_1)$, $\sim 16\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F) (\nu_2)$ and $27\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (P) (\nu_3)$. The ligand field parameters⁴ like Dq (918–1 120 cm^{-1}) ν_2/ν_1 (1.59–1.67), B' (832–966) and β (0.800–0.928) have been calculated. It is clear that the low values of ν_2/ν_1 support the octahedral nature of the Ni^{II} complexes. The percentages of distortion and the ligand field stabilisation energy (LFSE) values for the Ni^{II} complexes ($\sim 34\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) agree fairly well with the values reported for Ni^{II} . Further, the room temperature μ_{eff} values for the Ni^{II} complexes⁵ lie in the range 3.2–3.5 B.M. indicating distorted octahedral stereochemistry for the Ni^{II} complexes. Also the higher magnetic moment values compared to the spin-only value of 2.8 B.M. for Ni^{II} indicate some spin-orbit coupling.

The solution as well as solid state electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} -PMU complexes exhibit two bands at $\sim 11\,900$ and $\sim 30\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The broad band around $11\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition, which is characteristic of a distorted octahedral stereochemistry for a Cu^{II} complex. The intense absorption around $30\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is considered to be due to charge transfer transition. The Cu^{II} complexes have magnetic moment values ranging from 1.80 to 1.92 B.M. at room temperature pointing to the distorted octahedral geometry⁶ around Cu^{II} as well as the presence of one unpaired electron on the metal ion.

The TG and DTA data obtained for PMU and a few complexes show the thermal stability order to be $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMU} > \text{PMU} > \text{NiBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$, and the metal oxides being the final products. Kinetic parameters like activation energy (E^* , 13.8–37.5 kJ mol^{-1}), entropy of activation ($\Delta S^* - 229$ to $-241\text{ JK}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$) and frequency factor (Z , 3.5–15.5 s^{-1}) were evaluated using the Coats-Redfern equation⁶. The low Z values and negative ΔS^* values indicate the reactions to be slow and the activated complexes to have more orderly structures than the reactants⁷.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Thiosemicarbazone and 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Semicarbazone Complexes of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II)

BODH NARAIN JHA*, HARENDRA PRASAD YADAV
and

SITARAM ROY

Department of Chemistry, R. N. College, Hajipur-844 101

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WE report herein the preparation and characterisation of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene thiosemicarbazone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene semicarbazone.

Experimental

All the complexes and ligands were found to be insoluble in water and in most of the common organic solvents but soluble in acetone and methyl ethyl ketone. The metal ions and sulphur were analysed by reported methods¹. Electronic and ir spectra, elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibility (Gouy's method) were determined. Thermal studies were carried out in an air-oven to constant weight and the products characterised. All the reagents used were either of A.R or C.P. grade.

Preparation of ligands: 2-Hydroxy 1-naphthalidene semicarbazone was prepared by the reported method². 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene thiosemicarbazone was prepared as follows. Anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g) was added to powdered thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g) in distilled